

This basedata was constructed during the performing of experiments on pyrolysis process in pilot scale. In addition, a social-techno-economical assessment also was performed and the results are present in this work.

Product yields obtained in the five experiments performed in the continuous pyrolysis reactor.
Feed rate: 13 kg/h.

Experiment	1	2	3	4	5
Air stream (m ³ /h)	12	10	9	8	6
Recycled stream (m ³ /h)	0	2	3	4	6
Temperature (°C)	550	520	480	440	330
Charcoal (wt %)	15.64	15.30	16.20	17.40	15.40
Acid extract (wt %)	27.60	33.30	29.70	21.75	14.85
Bio-oil (wt %)	9.20	9.90	11.70	12.18	6.60
Pyrolysis gas (wt %)	39.56	31.50	32.40	35.67	18.15
LHV pyrolysis gas (MJ/Nm ³)	1.03	0.29	0.33	0.10	0.32
Tars and Heavy Hydrocarbons (wt %)*	8.00	10.00	10.00	13.00	45.00
Energy delivery potential (MJ/h)	60.1	60.8	66.9	71.0	54.3
(Equation 1)					
EEI (MJ/kg) (Equation 1)	35.9	29.5	34.5	35.9	11.2

(*): material removed during the reactor cleaning.

PEC for continuous pyrolysis unit and electricity generators.

Equipment	Correlation used	PEC (JUN/24 quotation)
Hammer mill	ICARUS correlation (Equation 2)	US\$ 12,740.00
Screw feeder	CAPCOAST correlation (Equation 3)	US\$ 273.00
Pyrolysis reactor	CAPCOAST correlation (Equation 3)	US\$ 14,615.00
Compressor (two)	ICARUS correlation (Equation 2)	US\$ 1,902.00
Cyclone	CAPCOAST correlation (Equation 3)	US\$ 1,709.00
Heat exchanger	CAPCOAST correlation (Equation 3)	US\$ 1,860.00
Fan	CAPCOAST correlation (Equation 3)	US\$ 6,907.00
Gas combustion chamber (*)	GUTHRIE correlation (Equation 4)	US\$ 37,185.00
Storage tank for gas (2 m ³)	Searched in supplier (**)	US\$ 3,849.00
Storage tanks for char, bio-oil and acid extract	Searched in supplier (**)	US\$ 83.30
Oil generator (Scenarios 1, 2 and 3)	Searched in supplier (**)	US\$ 14,060.00
Gas generator (Scenario 4)	Searched in supplier (**)	US\$ 43,940.00
Pelletizer	Searched in supplier (**)	US\$ 1,102.00

(*): employed only in Scenario 3. (**): this quotation was made in January/2025.

Main parameters of assessed pyrolysis generation scenarios.

Parameter	Scenario 1 (one shift)	Scenario 2 (two shifts)	Scenario 3 (two shifts)	Scenario 4 (two shifts)
Daily time of operation (h)	6.5	14.5	14.5	14.5
Daily biomass processed (h)	91.0	195.0	195.0	195.0
Daily char produced (kg)	14.7	32.8	32.8	32.8
Daily bio-oil produced (kg)	10.3	23.0	23.0	23.0
Daily acid extract produced (kg)	18.4	41.0	41.0	41.0
Daily pyrolysis gas produced (kg)	134.4	300.0	300.0	300.0
Daily energy consumed in pyrolysis unit (MJ)	185.0	390.4	391.2	391.2
Daily energy delivered by char (MJ)	329.4	734.7	734.7	734.7
Daily energy delivered by bio- oil (MJ)	183.2	408.7	408.7	408.7
Daily energy delivered by pyrolysis gas (MJ)	28.6	63.8	-	-
Daily potential energy delivered by pyrolysis plant (MJ)	541.2	1,207.2	1,143.4	1,143.4
Daily diesel consumption by generator (L)	89.1	178.2	178.2	-
Daily natural gas consumption by generator (m ³)	88.0	117.4	-	-
Daily LPG consumption by gas chamber (m ³)	-	-	0.38	0.38
Daily time operation for oil generator (h)	3.0	6.0	6.0	6.0
Daily time operation for gas generator (h)	6.0	8.0	-	-
Consumer units (CU's) benefited (*)	261	438	310	9
Renewable percentage	7.9	10.3	14.2	100.0
CU's supplied by renewable energy (basis: net energy)	20	45	40	9

(*)Considering CU electrical monthly consumption equal to 80 kWh (or 9.6 MJ).

Monetary comparison of projects to deliver electricity for Amazon communities.

	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 4
CAPEX (PDEC method)	US\$ 457,630.00		US\$ 427,640.00	US\$ 399,412.43
CAPEX (Lang method)	US\$ 451,635.00		US\$ 422,040.00	US\$ 394,180.78
OPEX (PDEC method) (*)	US\$ 153,570.00	US\$ 238,656.00	US\$ 203,023.00	US\$ 196,151.82
OPEX (Lang method) (*)	US\$ 141,470.00	US\$ 223,456.00	US\$ 207,750.00	US\$ 200,881.12
Photovoltaic kits for supplying the same CU's (**)	US\$ 4,926,538.00	US\$ 2,935,677.00	US\$ 3,486,820.00	US\$ 101,230.23
Time in years for photovoltaic investment is equal to pyrolysis unit investment disregarding annual monetary valorization/decrease. The value between parses is considering 10% a.y. of interest rate	16.1 (18.6)	18.7 (20.4)	15.1 (16.7)	The photovoltaic investment is better already in the year zero

(*): Attention should be paid because OPEX methodology is the same for both calculations, and not a particular property of these methodologies.

(**)The "Luz para Todos" program establishes photovoltaic kits of about US\$ 11.247,80. This kit is composed by four solar boards, one lithium battery, and electrical current alternator (Supp. Material)

Social-techno-economic assessment by attributes for both technologies.

Attributes	Generation by pyrolysis unit	Generation by photovoltaic kits	Justification
Lower fixed investment	1	0	The pyrolysis unit fixed investment is lower
Lower OPEX	0	1	The photovoltaic units certainly have lower OPEX
Local equipment purchase	1	0	The photovoltaic market in Brazil is still strongly dependent on external economies. On the other side, the pyrolysis unit was manufactured mostly with Brazilian equipment
Local return investment	1	0	The photovoltaic cells are imported
CU's benefitted/US\$ invested	0	1	The equivalence of investments occurs far from the photovoltaic cell's lifetime (25 years). So, the CU's supplied by this will be maintained for a longer time and for the same investment
Employability	1	0	The pyrolysis unit demands three workers per shift. The photovoltaic cells demand just two technicians for sporadic work
Local income	1	0	The photovoltaic cells technicians are itinerant
Formation demand	1	1	Both technologies need skilled workforce
Electricity renewability	0	1	The photovoltaic cells' energy are totally renewable
Harmless construction chain	1	0	The photovoltaic cells is more environmentally harmful
Waste generation	0	1	The photovoltaic cells is known for not producing waste

Waste disposal	0	1	The photovoltaic cells do not produce waste. The pyrolysis unit produces wastes and does not reuse all of them
Without electricity consumption	0	1	The photovoltaic cells do not consume electricity

Performances

Economic	0.6	0.4
Social	0.8	0.4
Environmental	0.2	0.8
SEEI	0.46	0.60

Lang factors for different type process.

Type of process medium	Lang factor
Solids medium	3,10
Solids and fluids medium	3,63
Fluids medium	4,74

Calculation routine in PDEC methodology.

Parameter	Percentage of Total purchased equipment Cost (TPEC)
Purchased equipment installation	39
Instrumentation and controls	26
Piping	10
Electrical systems	31
Buildings (including services)	47
Yard improvements	12
Service facilities	55
Total Investment Equipment Costs (TIEC)	TPEC*3,20
Engineering	32
Construction	34
Legal and contractor's fees	23
Contingency	0,15 *FCI
Total Investment Costs (TIC)	1,26 * TPEC
Fixed Capital Investment (FCI)	TIEC+TIC
Working capital (WC)	75

Total Cost Investment (TCI)

FCI + WC

Operation expenditures description.	
Direct Costs	Description
Annual salaries cost	Each turn (8 h) should have 3 employees. Two of them for plant operation (engineer + technical) and the third for administrative (four mensal salaries). \$266,78 mensal salary at NOV/2024
Technical supervision	This category was not accounted because the engineer and technical perform this
Raw material	This category was not accounted because considering biomass acquisition without charges
Diesel consumption	Consumed in oil generator. R\$ 6,39/Liter in JAN/2025. (https://frotas.localiza.com/blog/preco-do-diesel-no-brasil)
Natural gas consumption	Consumed in gas generator. R\$ 2,5307/Liter in DEZ/2024 (https://amazonas1.com.br/gas-natural-veicular-amazonas-tarifas-atualizadas-confira-valores/)
Cooling water	Zero cost because it is recycled in pyrolysis plant
Maintenance and repairs	6% of FI or FCI
Operating supplies	15% of previous one
Laboratory charges	5% of "Annual salaries cost"
Patents and Royalties	3% of TCI
Indirect Costs	
Packaging and storage	0,1 % of sum (annual salaries + supervision + maintenance). Just the char will be packed for send to a thermoelectric
Local taxes	1,5% of FCI or FI
Fees	5% of FCI or FI
Overhead Costs	
Administrative costs	3% of sum (direct costs + indirect costs)
Products distribution and sale	This category was not accounted because the products will not be commercialized
Research and development	5% of FCI or FI
OPEX annual	Direct costs + Indirect costs + Overhead costs

